

ENGLISH ROLE PLAY – WORKING FROM HOME

Topic:	<i>Home office regulations / Working from home</i>
Number of students:	<i>4</i>
Instructions for teacher:	<i>Introduce the topic first. Give all students the general brief and their role. Let them read the brief and prepare for the meeting (5 minutes). The meeting should take 20 to 25 minutes.</i>

GENERAL BRIEF

You work for a logistics company that organises the transport of goods to destinations all over the world. Since the beginning of the pandemic, you've introduced home office regulations. However, not everybody is happy with this development. The Managing Director has called a meeting to discuss the current regulations as well as measures that could be introduced to improve the situation.

ROLE 1: Managing Director

You come to work in the company every day and are a bit irritated that there are so few on your premises. Most of the offices are empty, even if they're usually occupied by only one person. As the government has suggested that people should work from home, respective regulations have been implemented in your company, too, meaning everybody can work from home, but you're a bit suspicious. Do employees really work effectively from home? Are some of them just using the new regulations as an excuse so they can improve their work life balance? In addition, you've read a study recently, outlining that working remotely also has disadvantages and you want to discuss them in this meeting. In general, you are not entirely happy with the solution and want to implement measures to evaluate if people really work effectively from home or implement an incentive scheme to make them come to the office again. You chair the meeting. Draw up and introduce an agenda. The following people participate in the meeting: you, the Head of Trade Union, the Head of Purchase and the Head of IT.

ROLE 2: Head of Trade Union

You think it's ridiculous that there's even a discussion about this topic. You know that most of the workers work really hard in their home offices. In addition, it's extremely difficult for employees with families to look after their quarantined kids while still having to complete all their professional tasks. You are against any control of the home office regulations, and you know that workers are easily offended when they have the feeling that they are not being trusted by management. While it is highly appreciated that people can work from home any additional control mechanisms could lead to a decrease in morale and commitment. Therefore, you are against any measures that supervise employees who work from home. Present alternatives that show that your employees are productive and nothing has to be changed about the current regulations.

ROLE 3: Head of Purchase

In general, you are in favour of working remotely. You like to use the new home office regulations to go for a run in your lunch break once in a while, but you're always available and you're irritated when your employees don't pick up the phone between 8am and 4pm. And to be honest, there have been problems within your department lately. People have reported to have been working long hours although many of them are not available for hours and don't call clients back. Others are online all the time and seem to be working more than usual. Somehow you want to identify the bad apples and supervise them more effectively without admitting to your Managing Director that you're having problems in your department. You also don't understand why people who have their own office want to work remotely, as the danger of being infected is very low when you don't share your office. You think that the best solution would be to implement general measures that can be implemented to reward people who work well from home and punish those who don't. Think of such measures and suggest them.

ROLE 4: Head of IT

You love working from home and you think your company should let people work from home even after the pandemic. This is a new incentive for employees and the only way to find good staff in this constant war for talent, especially in the IT sector. Lately, some of your best employees have left the company, as there are more favourable home office regulations in other companies. However, the company needs to invest in equipment – at the moment, employees have to use their own mobile phones to call customers and their own laptops / monitors as the company's laptops are too small. Your suggestion is to equip employees properly and when doing this, the company could also implement software that enables videocalls. You know that such a system could also be used to check if people are online / available or not. While you are against controlling people, you think that the entire equipment should be made more professional to improve working conditions and output.